

INCREASING EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. Various modern methods or interesting games are important in teaching elementary school students. For children at this age, anything new is considered interesting. A teacher teaches and educates, maybe a discoverer, a psychologist. Together with education, students' outlook, thinking ability is expanded, their thoughts and interests are explored.

Keywords: Pedagogical skill, novelty, game technology, "Blitz" game, initial questions.

INTRODUCTION

School education changes a child's lifestyle, social status, place in the class community and family environment. That is, play activities in the pre-school period alternate with study activities, which instills a sense of responsibility in the student. In this case, the content of primary education is inextricably linked with the student's interest in acquiring knowledge and the feeling of satisfaction from the result of his mental work.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

From this point of view, it is necessary to regularly monitor the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students, and to form the ability to use them in life, to fill the gaps in the knowledge of students in a timely manner, to create conditions for the regular development of the intellectual potential of talented students, to encourage students to work in cooperation with adults. interest in teaching, enriching pedagogical approaches and experiences aimed at protecting and strengthening their health, developing a plan of pedagogical activities outside the classroom, regular use of modern pedagogical technologies, the most advanced achievements of pedagogy in the process of education, establishing the cooperation of teachers with parents , implies the implementation of tasks such as the use of modern methods in the retraining of primary school teachers and regular improvement of their skills. [1.1654]

RESULTS

"Innovation" means newness. The result will be good if we create something innovative and give knowledge to elementary school students. In the educational process based on pedagogical technology, it is clearly defined within the framework of the activity of the teacher and the student. This shows a clear technology of educational organization. That is why it is today's task to introduce modern pedagogical technologies to the educational process, to increase the effectiveness of education. I often use Blitz-game technology in my classes. This technology is aimed at teaching students to correctly organize the sequence of actions, to think logically, to choose what they are learning from a wide variety of information.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

During this technology, students can transfer their independent thoughts to others, because this technology creates full conditions for this. This technology is implemented in seven stages. Students do it with great interest and it causes the subject to remain in their minds for a long time. The use of information technologies in lessons, the use of innovative ideas and new pedagogical technologies in their place increases the motivation of students to study, their curiosity, and the efficiency of independent work. Effective use of these requires a very high pedagogical skill from the teacher. We, the teachers, should always be in search and creation of news for our young students, and it is one of our most urgent tasks.[2,88]

Elementary school students, who have not yet been able to give up games, have a more playful, more cheerful nature. Therefore, it is appropriate to organize the lesson with various effective methods and interesting games.

There are a number of important activities to help elementary school students master the subjects, providing them with ample opportunities for advanced learning. These activities are used to increase students' motivation, develop thinking, and make the learning process interesting.

In the following sections, measures to further improve elementary school students' mastery of subjects are presented:

1. Lessons discussion

In order to keep elementary students interested in progress, it is important to provide student feedback during lessons. Students, by expressing themselves, how the material studied in the lesson may understand that they need to have modifications.

2. Initial Questions and Inspirational Information

Beginning each lesson with opening questions is an effective way to elicit student feedback and engage students. The opening questions provide an opportunity for students to search for answers to questions related to the topics in the lesson and to express their opinions.

Brainstorming half-hours during subject learning provides time designed to engage students and increase their interest in learning. During these half-hours, students can find the environment they need to exchange ideas with each other, ask questions, and absorb their knowledge. Actions to further improve elementary school students' mastery of subjects serve to inspire them to learn and help develop their thinking. These activities enhance students' advanced learning and inspire them to become more familiar with the subjects and to study further.[3,414-415]

It gives a positive result if it is used in lessons to repeat games and tasks or in reinforcement lessons. The choice of which type of game-task depends on the type of lesson, the level of training of students to perform games-tasks, their level of knowledge, opportunities for independent creative work, the ability to quickly recall what they have learned, and the degree to which creativity is formed. "Brainstorming", "Thoughtstorming", "Networks" methods are used in education today.

Sinkwain, BBB, Five Plus, 6x6x6, Debate, Role Play, FSMU, Small Group Work, Rounded Snow, Zigzag, Last So Modern technologies such as "zni men aytay" are used.

CONCLUSIONS

In our opinion, the main requirements for educational games are as follows:

1. Educational games should be suitable for the age of students;
2. The games should be proportionate to the content of the topic being played;

3. The time of educational games must be clearly defined;
4. Educational games should have both educational and educational value;
5. The purpose and significance of educational games should be determined.

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